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Impact of sowing density and harvesting management on pattern of hard seed breakdown in alfalfa (*Medicago scutellata*)

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate the effects of deferred harvesting, sowing density and harvest intensity on hard seed and breakdown trend of an annual medic (*Medicago scutellata* var. Robinson), an experiment was conducted in the Research Farm of Agriculture Faculty, Tehran University in Karaj, Iran during the 2005 growing season. The experimental factors were arranged in split-split plots based on a complete randomized block design with four replications. The method of harvesting (continues or deferred), the sowing density (25, 75 and 225 plants/m²) and the harvest intensity (cutting from ground level of 2, 4 and 8 cm) were allotted to the main, split and split-split plots, respectively. The results showed that present hard seedness followed a decreasing trend when sowing density decreased and harvest intensity increased. Present hard seedness was 83.3% in August during harvest of pods which was decreased to 52.7% in March. After harvesting, present hard seedness decreased in all treatments. These results suggest that when low sowing rate and severe defoliation decrease the seed production (data not shown), plants increase hard seed breakdown for fast regeneration and survive in next years which can be noted as a pasture management strategy.

Key words : Alfalfa, hard seed breakdown, harvest intensity, sowing density

INTRODUCTION

Medicago scutellata had been sown in the 250-450 mm mean annual rainfall zones of South Australia with Mediterranean-type climates. Their ability to persist under harsh rainfall and grazing conditions by having high levels of hard seed have encouraged their widespread utilization in semi-arid areas of South Australia and regions with similar Mediterranean climatic conditions in the world (Chaichi *et al.*, 1996). Annual medics pastures have been used successfully for many years in ley-farming systems (Crawford and Nankivell, 1989; Aydin and Uzun and 2001; Uzun and Aydin, 2004). Hard seedness is an ecological characteristic of annual medic species which is broken down due to temperature fluctuation and pod position in the soil. Annual medics are the most suitable legumes for the ley-farming system in Iran as they naturally occur in all regions and are well adapted to alkaline soils. The high percentage of hard seed over 90% in some species of Iranian medics makes them well adapted in

rotation with cereals and gives them the ability to carry through the crop phase successfully and regenerate in the following years. Cultivars with less hard seedness at the seasonal break increase the plant density and thus the competitiveness and productivity of the medic-based pasture (Taylor, 1996). Medic seed reserves of 200 kg/ha following a cropping sequence was considered the critical minimum seed reserve was required to maintain the stability of self-generating medic pasture in ley-farming system (Carter, 1983). The objectives of this experiment were to examine the effects of sowing rate (self-regeneration ability), defoliation intensity (simulating grazing pressure) and method of harvesting (simulating grazing deferment) on hard seed and breakdown trend of annual medic (*Medicago scutellata* var. Robinson).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Site of Experiment

The experiment was carried out at the

Research Farm of College of Agriculture, University of Tehran during 2005 growing season. The site is located at 35° 25' N latitude, 71° 25' E longitudes and an altitude of 1321 m above sea level. Karaj is located about 30 km west of Tehran thus has a semi-arid climate with 375 mm yearly rainfall. The soil of experimental site was clay loam with a clay type of montmorillonite, low in nitrogen (0.08-0.09%), low in organic matter (0.7-0.8%) and alkaline in reaction with a pH of 8 and electrical conductivity 0.39 dS/m.

Planting and Preparation of the Experimental Site

The seed of *M. scutellata* var. Robinson had hard seedness. So, planting was done on 14 April 2005 after scarification. The area of every plot was 4 m². Normal cultural practice was followed uniformly for all experimental units. The plots were hand-weeded in different vegetative stages. Irrigation was applied at weekly interval. The fertilizer of urea was top-dressed at planting time (25 kg/ha) and at eight leaves stage (25 kg/ha).

Experimental Design and Treatments

The experimental factors were arranged in split-split plots based on a complete randomized block design with four replications. Where the management of harvesting (continues and deferred) was allocated to main plot, the sowing density (25, 75 and 225 plants/m²) to split plots and the harvest intensity (cutting from ground level of 2, 4 and 8 cm) to the split-split plots.

Measurements

All measurements were done on a central area of 100 × 100 cm within each sown plot, while all defoliation treatments were applied on sown plots of 200 × 200 cm. A buffer zone of 100 cm was left all around each micro plot to prevent any border effects. The first defoliation for the continuous defoliation treatment was done on 26 May 2005, as soon as plants established. Deferred defoliation treatments started two weeks later on 16 June 2005. At each harvest, plants were cut with a hedge trimmer fitted with a catcher. To ensure defoliation at the correct height the hedge

trimmer rested on a wooden frame of 2, 4 or 8 cm height. Dry weight samples were oven-dried at 60°C to a constant weight to determine dry forage yield, available forage and growth on a dry weight basis.

Hard Seedness Tests

After harvesting times which were done from August to March, 25 pods were collected from the areas of each plot to determine changes in hard seedness. After brief storage in the laboratory, each sample was allocated to a Petri dish and labelled. All Petri dishes contained 10 mm cotton wool on the bottom and one piece of filter paper on the top of the seeds. Germination tests were continued for 10 days in a humidified incubator at 20°C. Germination determines the number and proportion of hard seeds. Analyses of variance were made on all measured and derived variables and using the SAS program on selected plant variables. Data were transformed whenever required to stabilize the variance. Error bars on graphs refer to standard error of means, unless otherwise stated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Present Hard Seedness

System of defoliation (continues or deferred) did not show significant impact on present hard seedness but sowing density and defoliation intensity had a significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on present hard seedness (Table 1). The highest present hard seedness was achieved at high sowing rate and reduced as sowing rate decreased at all samples (August to March). This result suggests that in lower plant density, better light interception and distribution in canopy during seed filling period cause more available assimilates and bigger seeds with less hard seedness (Patane and Grista, 2006). In this experiment, minimum hard seedness was obtained at lowest sowing density. Present hard seedness in plots with 25 plants/m² as compared with other plots lessened about 24% in March (Fig. 1). Also As harvest intensity increased present hard seedness followed a decreasing trend. The maximum hard seedness was obtained from highest intensity harvest from ground level.

Table 1. Summary of ANOVA analysis on the effects of defoliation system, sowing rate and defoliation intensity on forage yield, pod yield, seed yield and hard seedness of *Medicago scutellata*

Time of sampling	Source of variation						
	DS	SR	DI	DS x SR	DS x DI	SR x DI	DS x SR x DI
August	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
September	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
October	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
November	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
December	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
January	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
February	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS
March	NS	***	***	NS	***	NS	NS

NS : Not Significant, *** P<0.001. DS : Defoliation system, SR : Sowing rate, DI : Defoliation intensity.

Fig. 1. Effect of sowing rate on hard seedness after pod harvesting. Fig. 2. Effect of defoliation intensity on hard seedness after pod harvesting.

In contrast, in harvest heights of 4 and 8 cm from ground level obtained maximum hard seedness (Fig. 2). There was a significant ($P<0.001$) interaction between sowing rate and defoliation intensity on present hard seedness. As sowing density decreased and harvest intensity increased, present hard seedness followed a decreasing trend (Fig. 3). The proportion of present soft seed on lowest sowing rate and severe defoliation was maximum in August (during harvest of pods) and sampling after that. Because seed production is the lowest on low sowing rate and severe defoliation, plants with this device increase soft seed for regeneration and survive in next years (Chaichi *et al.*, 1996; Malo, 2000). The results of this experiment support the findings of Quigley and Carter (1989) who demonstrated that removal of residues increased the exposure of the pods to fluctuating temperatures under more severe defoliation then decreased present hard

seedness. (Quigley and Carter, 1989; Nadafi *et al.*, 2006). But in their experiment, significant correlations did not exist between residues of plants and hard seedness ($R^2=0.18$). Disturbance of weed and not control of weed after harvesting caused to create equal condition on all treatments. However, correlations between residues of plants and hard seedness were not significant. Agronomic condition at growing season affects more than environmental condition on hard seedness after harvest of pod, this is in agreement with the results obtained by Taylor (1996).

Breakdown of Hard Seedness in Pods

There was a decline in hard seedness with time from the maturation of the pods in August 2005 to March 2006 (Fig. 4). It suggests that less germination of early season seeds may be due to not only hard seed coat but also higher levels of germination inhibitor or

Fig. 3. Interaction of defoliation intensity and sowing rate on hard seedness after harvesting.

Fig. 4. Breakdown of hard seedness in annual *Medicago scutelatta* var. Robinson after harvesting.

immature embryo in the seeds (Vilela and Ravetta 2002; Koyuncu, 2005). The per cent of soft seed was low following pod maturation in August (less than 7%). There was an increasing trend in breakdown of hard seedness with increase in the post-maturation period. The highest per cent of soft seed (higher than 80%) was achieved in March 2006 at the severe intensity defoliation in the low sowing rate (Fig. 3). However, the other treatments were not significantly different in all samples (Fig. 3). After harvesting, presence of hard seedness decreased in all the treatments. Presence of hard seedness was 83.3 in August (during harvest of pods) which decreased to 52.7 in March (Fig. 4). The gradual trend of

breakdown of hard seedness (although at different rates) supports the statement of Cocks (2004) and Shabani and Chaichi (2004) indicating that many medics lose hard seedness late in the season. Decline of breakdown of hard seedness was not constant from sampling in a month to next month. The maximum decline of hard seedness occurs between December and January (Fig. 4). At this time the amount of rains was high, breakdown of hard seedness occurs higher than other sampling times. These results are in agreement with the findings of Brahim and Smith (1993) who studied four cultivars of annual medic and demonstrated that the proportion of soft seed was 5% less in summer

which increased to commencement of rain at autumn (Baes *et al.*, 2002). The lower hard seedness and more germination might be due to more level of gibberellin in seed during the cold season (Ogawa *et al.*, 2003). The results of this experiment support the findings of Lloyd *et al.* (1998) and Koyuncu (2005) who demonstrated that breakdown of hard seedness increased with time from the maturation of the pods and maximum breakdown of hard seedness occurred in January.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The seeds of *Medicago scutellata* have been produced in August under low sowing density and deferred and high intensity harvesting management can be used for synthetic survival of pastures during December to January.
2. When low sowing rate and severe defoliation decrease the seed production, plants increase hard seed breakdown for fast regeneration and survive in next years which can be noted as a pasture management strategy.

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